

ORFG Funder Policy Landscape Report and Recommendations: 2026

An analysis of philanthropic funder policies on open research outputs and open practices

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Open Research Funders Group

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
About the Open Research Funders Group	3
Purpose & Scope	3
Findings	3
Recommendations for Funder Policies	5
Next steps	7
2026 Funder Policy Landscape Report and Recommendations	8
Introduction	8
Findings & Discussion	10
Policy Development and Growth Since 2023	24
Recommendations for Funder Policies	25
Next Steps	28
Acknowledgments	29
Appendices	30
Appendix A: Methods and Scope	30
Appendix B: Data Dictionary	32
Appendix C: Funders with Publicly Available Policies	34
Appendix D: Licenses	35

Executive Summary

About the Open Research Funders Group

The [Open Research Funders Group \(ORFG\)](#) is a community of philanthropic funders that seeks to advance open science by increasing sharing and collaboration across the global research enterprise. Members work together to develop policies and practices that can accelerate the pace of discovery, reduce information-sharing gaps, and promote reproducibility. Funders also extend their influence through ORFG by impacting policy, institutions, and furthering dialogues on open research.

Purpose & Scope

In order to better understand current funder policies for open outputs, ORFG analyzed philanthropic funders' access-to-research (or open research) policies. For this report, access-to-research policies are defined as those written policies governing researcher behaviors to make research results readily available, including but not limited to policies requiring or suggesting deposition of narrative results, data, and code into repositories. These policies may also govern rights retention, licensing terms, and more. By understanding the scope of policies, ORFG can identify policy trends and gaps, and assist in the development of strategies to further open practices. This information will also help identify the resources funders need as they socialize and implement open practices and policies within their organizations and among communities, such as grantees, board members, and the general public.

This analysis tracked policy requirements for research outputs and practices, including but not limited to articles, preprints, code, data, data management plans, tangible materials, and more. It did not specifically track book outputs, as very few funders specify books in their policies. The 2026 analysis expanded upon previous analyses and included non-ORFG member funders.

Findings

This analysis and exercise was developed with the understanding that funder policies must serve the approach and strategies of the funding organization. It is important to note that whether or not a funder has a policy does not necessarily signal a lack of interest or commitment to research outputs. Rather, funders employ a wide variety of strategies and approaches to accomplish their goals.

It is also important to note the tension between the dominant publishing models and the ideals of open practices. Funders must support researchers operating in the current research paradigm, yet also have the flexibility and strategic will to experiment with new funding models and open practices.

This analysis included thirty-nine funders, twenty-five of which have policies available for analysis.

Specific findings:

- Funders use a variety of policy approaches to encourage and/or require open sharing of outputs.
- Policies are trending to more often requiring open outputs rather than simply recommending them.
- Adoption of access to article requirements (either open or public access) has increased from 52% in 2023 to 76% in 2026.
- Compared to the 2023 analysis, adoption of preprint requirements has increased by 18%.
- Data deposition is a common requirement, with adoption increasing by 3% since 2023.
- Requirements for data management plans and for data to meet FAIR standards lag behind data deposition requirements.
- There is low uptake on recommendations or policy requirements for persistent identifiers (PIDs), including for funders and awards. Yet there are numerous initiatives and coalitions in the open ecosystem that would enhance or support funder PID adoption. Funders have an opportunity to take advantage of the wealth of knowledge and support that exists in this arena.

Recommendations for Funder Policies

The following five recommendations stem from the analysis and highlight logical next steps for policy improvements and/ or “low hanging fruit” that will support improvements in the open research and open output ecosystem.

1. Eliminate embargo periods

U.S. Federal funding agencies have developed and are currently implementing policies requiring the immediate sharing of research outputs and prohibiting embargo periods. Embargo periods impede the progress of discovery. In a rapidly changing scientific and knowledge production environment, embargos introduce additional barriers to accessing knowledge.

2. Partner with open infrastructure providers

There are numerous initiatives and infrastructure providers that can support funders in implementing open practices. For example, most repositories for data, preprints, and other outputs assign persistent identifiers that can be made openly available and are machine-readable. Using open metadata such as ROR IDs, ORCID iDs, and DOIs would enable better monitoring of funder impacts and research outputs tied to awards as well as enable user discovery. Providers that assign and track PIDs are just one example in this category. Others may include search providers, publishing platforms, preprint servers, licensing standards, peer review communities, Open Educational Resource (OER) tools and more.

3. Expand data management plan requirements and support existing data principles and practices

Data sharing rapidly increases the progress of knowledge and research. Yet without thoughtful sharing that optimizes data discovery and usability, shared data cannot accelerate knowledge discovery. Instead, it may instead lead to wasted effort as researchers reproduce datasets for new analyses. Expanding data deposition policies to support or require the use of FAIR data practices would mitigate the sharing of data that cannot be used in future research due to integrity issues or

other data quality problems. Moreover, supporting the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance will ensure that research data does not perpetuate further harm to indigenous people. Finally, data sharing requirements that translate into adopted practice are most successful when supported by robust training, education, and guidance to support awardees in meeting these expectations.

4. Strategically accelerate preprint adoption

The largest area of growth in funder policy open output adoption is the requirement or recommendation to share preprints. This is exemplified by the existing [Preprint Policy Framework](#) hosted by ASAPbio and created by the Creative Commons Open Science team in collaboration with funders and research-performing organizations. Preprints allow a decoupling of research sharing and research evaluation processes from the commercial publishing enterprise. Moreover, transparent peer review practices, data, and other research output sharing practices are currently being built for the preprint space. Given that the research and information-sharing landscape is rapidly changing in response to both political and technological disruptions, adopting preprint policies - either to replace or complement traditional open access policies - will ensure funders can readily participate in future innovations such as modular science and research sharing.

5. Develop incentives and workflows to complement policy requirements

Policy requirements are one strategy to ensure open practice adoption. However, they should be instituted alongside complementary open practice incentives and workflows. Incentives are also a mechanism that can be used by funders, regardless of whether or not they have codified policies supporting open research.

While some researchers may be motivated by the altruism of open practice, others may be more extrinsically motivated. Introducing extrinsic motivations beyond policy compliance, such as public acknowledgment or commendations for open practices, may further incentivize adoption of open practices. As a complement, workflows that allow for ease of open practice implementation, such as processes for data deposit or compliance and reporting workflows, can signal the need for and support the adoption of open practices.

Next steps

ORFG plans to use this document to encourage implementation and socialization of open output practices and the development of funder access-to-research policies. The report will be publicly shared and socialized to begin conversations in the open output community.

To support funders in implementing recommendations, ORFG will identify, share, and develop the necessary resources.

2026 Funder Policy Landscape Report and Recommendations

Introduction

The [Open Research Funders Group \(ORFG\)](#) is a community of philanthropic funders that seeks to advance open science by increasing sharing and collaboration across the global research enterprise. Members work together to develop policies and practices that can accelerate the pace of discovery, reduce information-sharing gaps, and promote reproducibility. Funders also extend their influence through ORFG by impacting policy, institutions, and furthering dialogues on open research.

Access-to-research policies are one mechanism philanthropic funders use to ensure the research they support benefits society. For this report, access-to-research policies are defined as written policies that govern researcher behavior to make research results readily available, including, but not limited to, policies requiring or suggesting the deposition of narrative results, data, and code into repositories. These policies may also govern rights retention, licensing terms, and more.

Access to research also supports the growth of knowledge and expansion of science by allowing researchers to build upon previous research findings. Access to research benefits the public, whose health, welfare, and other social problems can be improved by evidence-based policy and practice implementation. Policies can codify desired open research practices that will meet these funders' aims.¹

Many philanthropic funders have access-to-research policies that codify open practices internally and for their awardees. The ORFG community supports funders in the development and implementation of these policies. As a community members engage in knowledge exchange, community support, and extend influence all in the name of improving the open research ecosystem. Currently funders and others engaged in the research ecosystem are thinking about how to advance open practices that are fit for purpose and respond to the rapidly changing research landscape. In the United States the 2022 Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP)

¹ For discussions of these practices, see the Center for Open Science's [Open Science web page](#), or [UNESCO's Recommendation on Open Science](#).

memo [Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research](#), accelerated the rapidity with which researchers are mandated to make their research publicly available by requiring Federal agencies to update their public access policies “...to make publications and their supporting data resulting from federally funded research publicly accessible without an embargo on their free and public release,”² among other requirements. Additionally, several philanthropic funders have changed and updated their access-to-research policies. Gates Foundation, Howard Hughes Medical Institute (HHMI), Michael J. Fox foundation, and Astera Institute are all examples of funders that have recently implemented or updated policies requiring awardees to engage in open practices. Moreover, the current US and global political landscape and development of new technologies such as generative artificial intelligence have caused significant disruptions to the open ecosystem.

This funder policy landscape analysis builds upon previous data collection and analysis completed in 2023 in order to better understand funder policies for open outputs. Now three years later we see differences in policy requirements and different needs to support funders in the current research landscape. The scope of the 2023 analysis was expanded to include funders beyond those that are current ORFG members. It includes current, past, and prospective ORFG members, namely philanthropic funders with a vested interest in open research outputs and open practices. By understanding the scope of funder policies, ORFG can identify policy trends and gaps and assist in the development of strategy development to further open practices. This information will also support the identification of needed resources to support funders as they socialize and implement open practices and policies within their organizations and their stakeholders such as grantees, board members, and the general public.

The 2026 analysis also expanded the data included. Additional information gathered includes the use of identifiers for people, outputs, funders and awards, as well as PID registry memberships and grant tracking and management systems. By including these additional data points, the 2026 analysis provides a broader picture of the open policies and practices undertaken across the funder landscape. It will also support coalition initiatives in the broader open research

² Alondra Nelson, “Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research,” Memo, August 25, 2022, <https://bidenwhitehouse.archives.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/08/08-2022-OSTP-Public-Access-Memo.pdf>.

community, such as the [Barcelona Declaration on Research Information](#), as well as infrastructure providers and community champions such as [openRxiv](#) and [ASAPbio](#), respectively. These coalitions and groups are engaging in parallel work, and the findings of this analysis will be shared with them.

Findings & Discussion

This report section combines analysis findings and discussion. (For analysis methods, scope, and limitations see [Appendix A: Methods and Scope](#).) We first present policies generally, discussing variations on policy approaches as well as the social and political context and nuance of policy implementation at funders. We then discuss research outputs in the order in which they have been formally adopted by funders. Finally, we examine persistent identifiers and their supporting systems.

Policies

Of the thirty-nine funders investigated, 25 (64%) have access-to-research policies or other policies mentioning output suggestions or requirements. A list of publicly available funder policies is listed in [Appendix C: Funder with Publicly Available Policies](#). While this percentage may seem small for ORFG members and other funders of open outputs, it is important to note that the lack of access-to-research policy does not necessarily signal a lack of interest or commitment to research outputs. Rather, funders employ a wide variety of strategies and approaches to accomplish their goals. While some funders have detailed policies, such as [Aligning Science Across Parkinson's \(ASAP\) Open Science Policy Handbook](#),³ other funders do not fund traditional research outputs such as articles and data that enable researchers to easily comply with rigid policies. For example, funders may support open educational materials, the development of social policies, or applied practices in the K-12 educational system that are not easily put into policy frameworks. Moreover, some funders' funding strategies specifically prioritize open projects, and they see no need to develop access-to-research policies for awardees. Finally, once developed, policies must be adhered to, which takes staff time and other resources to monitor and enforce policy compliance.

³ Aligning Science Across Parkinson's, "ASAP Open Science Policy Handbook," Zenodo, December 17, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17968591>.

Some funders are in various stages of actively developing their policies or awaiting leadership sign-off on proposed open policies. Another contextual nuance affecting the presence or lack of access-to-research policies could be determined by the mechanisms funders use to disperse funds. For example, some funders analysed use “pass through” funding, where they fund projects that seek to re-grant their dollars. As such they can have little influence and cannot exert robust compliance mechanisms on research produced. And finally, different financial mechanisms for funding may affect how policies can be worded and implemented.

While some philanthropic funders use large endowments to make grants, a growing number of funders use donor-advised funds to make gifts, which may be subject to different regulatory requirements governing what can and cannot be included in policies attached to the transfer of funds. One way that funders can express open research interests to awardees of donor-advised funds is to make recommendations regarding open practices, but can hold no compliance on awardees for the duration of the award. These funders can, however, consider whether recommendations were enacted prior to awarding funds in the future.

Other legalities can affect the contents and scope of access-to-research policies. For example, clinical trials are heavily regulated and as such funder policies often align with federal regulations to require clinical trial pre-registration. Research is often funded by multiple sources, including philanthropic and public awards. As such, funders may align policies to at least match public requirements, which enables researcher compliance with government funding regulations.

Finally, it should be mentioned that the development of access-to-research policies at philanthropic funders must take into account the funders’ risk management strategies. There are nuanced politics internally and externally, and funders must ensure that all stakeholders, whether it is the foundation’s board or its awardees, are socialized and aware of access-to-research requirements.

Research Outputs

Access-to-research policies vary in their detail in respect to what to share and how to share it. Some policies dive deeply into detail for multiple output types, while others provide succinct

requirements. The kinds of projects funded and organizational approaches and strategies to funding heavily influence their policies.

Unsurprisingly, the majority of funder policies require article sharing. This is likely due to the nature of the research sharing ecosystem, which began with the sharing of open access articles and has since developed to encompass more robust open practices. The following chart shows how policies address varying research outputs, indicating whether each output’s openness is as a requirement, suggestion, both, or treated differently. A further detailed analysis and discussion of each output follows.

Article Outputs

This section presents findings and discusses the sharing of articles. It does not present findings on preprints, which are addressed in the [Preprints section](#) of this report.

Open article sharing is the output most often required in the policies analyzed. This is largely due to the fact that the sharing of articles has come a long way with policies created by, monitored, and enforced by funders of all kinds. The 2008 National Institutes of Health Public Access Policy,

was a critical moment that led this change in the United States. Since that time, U.S. public access-to-research policies expanded to include more funding agencies such as the National Science Foundation, the Department of Energy, the Department of Transportation, and others. In 2022 the OSTP directed agencies to plan and create policy for immediate sharing of research articles and data (rather than allowing embargoed access) to be implemented no later than December 31, 2025.

Of the policies, nineteen require access to articles (76%), three suggest access to articles (12%), and one (4%) discusses articles in a different context.

Article Sharing			
Required	Suggested	Other	Total
19	3	1	23

The gap between the number of funders with policies and those policies that directly suggest or require article sharing is largely based on one of two factors. First is policy opacity; either the funder did not provide the policy for analysis, or no formal codified policy could be found, even though it is known that open policies and practices. Second, a funder’s approach assumes an open practice and therefore, has a “light touch” in terms of policy detail.

It should also be noted that this analysis is coded for article access without a distinction between public access and open access.⁴ Qualitatively, it was found that of the nineteen with required article access, eighteen of those required included open access, and one only required public access in accordance with the NIH Public Access Policy.

While both the context of policies that either required or mention article sharing position sharing articles or as a way to make outputs openly available, the one policy coded as “other” outrightly prohibits the use of funder’s dollars to create journal articles. This approach aims to disrupt the scholarly publishing system. “In an effort to build for a more abundant, open future, Astera will no

⁴ Public access refers to making articles freely available, usually in the form of an author accepted manuscript as required by a public funding agency, whereas open access refers to making a postprint or final published article freely available.

longer support this journal-centric world. Explicitly, we will not allow Astera time or funds to be used to contribute directly to journal articles.”⁵

Of the twenty-one funders whose policies positively mention article access, fifteen (71%) explicitly discuss embargo periods. Eleven (52%) of those prohibit embargos, and four (19%) policies specify embargo periods ranging from six to twelve months, one of which distinguishes between article publications (no embargo allowed) and monograph chapters or monographs (six-month exception to the no embargo period). There are a variety of factors that may influence funders’ acceptance of embargos as applied to research outputs. The common twelve-month maximum embargo period reflects what public federal funding agencies have supported in the United States (up until December 31, 2025) and in other countries such as Denmark, where its [National Strategy for Open Access](#) states a maximum embargo period of twelve months.⁶

Embargos in Funder Policies		
Prohibited	Allowed	Total
11	4	15

Allowable Embargos in Funder Policies		
Articles	Monographs	Total
3	1	4

Despite the minority allowance for embargos, it is likely that funders will shorten or prohibit embargoes in accordance with federal policies, or begin recommending or requiring preprint deposit. Preprint deposit is discussed in further detail in the [preprints section](#) of this report.

The final facet of funder policies for article sharing is article license requirements. Seven funders requiring or suggesting open articles do not mention specific licenses, whereas sixteen specify

⁵ Astera Institute, *Astera Open Science Policy*, May 30, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15548989>.

⁶ “Open Access Policy, Danish National Research Foundation,” *Danish National Research Foundation*, n.d., accessed February 17, 2026, <https://dg.dk/en/open-access-policy>.

licenses, the majority of which are variations of Creative Commons (CC) licenses. Two funders use more generic language specifying “open” or “open access” licenses. For a comprehensive list of licenses mentioned in funder policies, see [Appendix D: Licenses](#).

Data

Like the U.S. National funders, philanthropic funder policies also outline data deposit requirements. Of the twenty-five existing policies, sixteen (64%) suggest or require access to data. This output type is the second-highest in requirement adoption. While data access is required, only a little over half of those policies requiring data access require a plan to guide the responsible stewardship of that data using data management plans. Similarly, the number of policies that stipulate data must be in accordance with the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles⁷ lags behind in the number of data access requirements.

Depositing data is increasingly seen as an important way to share research outputs, yet it must be done properly with data that is clean and usable for it to be able to speed the rapidity of discovery

⁷ “FAIR Principles,” *GO FAIR*, n.d., accessed February 17, 2026, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles>.

and reproducibility. As such, many funders work to support researchers in their data deposit by offering training on data deposit, the FAIR data principles, and other aspects of data management, as exemplified by the American Heart Association (AHA)⁸. In addition to listing compliant data repositories, the AHA offers [Sample Data Plans](#), and requires grantees from select programs to undergo open science training that help to socialize and support their open science requirements, including data deposit. One unique example of foundation support for data deposit is the support provided to funded researchers provided by the Alex’s Lemonade Stand Foundation (ALSF) [Childhood Cancer Data Lab](#). This lab is a team of scientists, engineers, and designers that will take the awardee data to prepare it for deposit and make it discoverable via their projects and portals, as well as provide training on data science.

A complement to FAIR data practices are the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance, which provide a framework for data sharing that considers power differentials, as well as social and historical contexts that have perpetuated harms against indigenous people.⁹ None of the policies reviewed mentions the CARE Principles.

In addition to requiring or suggesting data deposit, some funder policies also require or recommend specific data licenses. While FAIR compliant data practices do incorporate the need for data to be open and reusable, FAIR does not require specific licenses, rather mandates, “The conditions under which the data can be used should be clear to machines and humans.”¹⁰

Data Licenses		
	Number of Funders	Licenses Mentioned
FAIR and Specific License Suggestions/Requirements	7	CCO CCO + BY CC-BY CC-BY 4.0 CC-BY-SA Conformant licenses

⁸ “Open Science Policy Statements for AHA Funded Research,” Professional.Heart.Org, accessed February 17, 2026, <https://professional.heart.org/en/research-programs/awardee-resources/open-science-policy-statements-for-aha-funded-research>.

⁹ “CARE Principles,” Global Indigenous Data Alliance, accessed March 6, 2026, <https://www.gida-global.org/care>.

¹⁰ “R1.1: (Meta)Data Are Released with a Clear and Accessible Data Usage License,” *GO FAIR*, n.d., accessed March 4, 2026, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/r1-1-metadata-released-clear-accessible-data-usage-license>.

		“No more restrictive than CC-BY” CC license
FAIR without license mentions	4	N/A
Specific Licenses Listed without FAIR Suggestions or requirements	4	CCO CC-BY CC-BY-SA CC license “CC-BY or equivalent”
Data sharing recommended or required, no license specifications, no FAIR suggested or required	5	N/A

For a comprehensive list of licenses mentioned in funder policies see [Appendix D: Licenses](#).

Code

Source code for software is another research output discussed by funders’ policies. Of the twenty-five policies, twelve (48%) require code sharing and three (12%) suggest code sharing. Eight of those discussing code sharing offer licensing guidance, stipulating or recommending licenses that allow for code sharing and reuse. One code-sharing concern expressed by HHMI’s policy addresses financial burdens to access code.¹¹

“The author(s) may provide executable files and source code under a license agreement with restrictions comparable to those of an MTA, as long as the executable files or source code are available at no or minimal cost to academic and nonprofit scientists for research use and with no restriction on the research projects or field of research in which they may be used.

Charging academic and nonprofit scientists for access to an enhanced version of software with upgrades and user support is permitted.”

For a comprehensive list of licenses mentioned in funder policies see [Appendix D: Licenses](#).

¹¹ “Publishing and Sharing | HHMI,” accessed February 17, 2026, <https://www.hhmi.org/about/policies/publishing-sharing>.

Preprints

The policies analyzed show a marked increase in the suggestion or requirement of preprint deposit. Of the funders with policies, eight (32%) require preprints and five (20%) mention preprints in their policies.

Preprints		
Required	Suggested	Total
8	6	14

Funders recommending or requiring preprint deposit cite the need for immediacy of research results sharing, which is often not enabled when publishing in OA journals that rely on article processing charges (APCs) to make articles openly available. As an example, HHMI’s policy states, “Shifting the focus to preprints addresses these challenges and encourages a more transparent scholarly ecosystem in which researchers have more control over dissemination of their scholarship. In light of this shifted focus, the policy also defines how HHMI research budgets may be used to support manuscript-related services offered by scientific publishers.”¹²

It is noticeable that preprint deposit is the most recommended practice in funder policies. (See the output comparison chart in the main [Research Outputs](#) section of this report.) This is likely due to the growing interest in preprints as a way to immediately share research, as well as the increasingly adopted publish, review, curate model¹³ of research sharing and research publication, such as enabled by initiatives and preprint repositories such as [PREreview](#), [ASAPbio](#), [openRxiv](#), and [arXiv](#), for example. Several of those funders that require preprints are no longer allowing the use of award funds to pay for APCs, such as the Gates Foundation. As such, preprint recommendations in access-to-research policies are one way that funders may be slowly socializing their policies with an eye to future policy requirements.

¹² “Publishing and Sharing | HHMI.”

¹³ *Peer-Reviewed Preprints and the Publish-Review-Curate Model | Plan S*, n.d., accessed February 19, 2026, <https://www.coalition-s.org/blog/peer-reviewed-preprints-and-the-publish-review-curate-model>.

Additionally, several funders have signed onto the [Preprint Policy Framework](#), making their funding policies transparent, and advocating for the further adoption of preprints as an advancement for the immediate sharing of open research outputs.

One of the most difficult challenges of funders moving toward preprint culture is tied to the incentive culture for researchers affiliated with higher educational institutions. Most tenure and promotion processes privilege the publication of research outputs that have undergone formal peer reviewer processes in traditional journals as a marker of quality and impact. This culture has been slow to adapt and to embrace open practices such as preprint deposit, open peer review, and publish, review, curate models of research sharing.

Finally, it should be noted that Astera, which disincentivizes journal publication and prohibits “using Astera funds or time to contribute (whether as an author or otherwise) directly to the creation of journal publications,” does allow preprint deposit. Astera’s policy also promotes the use of sharing research findings using non archival and non peer reviewed platforms such as Substack and Medium, provided archival copies are posted in [Zenodo](#). It also supports the creation of [Nanopublications](#) for “single data point or assertion.”

Protocols and Tangible Materials

Some funders see sharing of protocols and tangible materials (genetic sequences, reagents, etc.) as an important part of open research practice. Openly sharing both protocols and tangible materials enables replication studies and allows for both protocols and materials to be used in new, innovative research that quickly builds upon knowledge gained through previous studies. Sharing of tangible materials is often disease-specific, and as such adopted mostly by funders of biomedical research. With ten (40%) policies mentioning or requiring protocol sharing and thirteen (52%) mentioning or requiring tangible material sharing, this is a decent adoption, since not all funders offer granular policies or fund research using bench protocols and producing or using tangible materials.

Protocol Sharing		
Required	Suggested	Total
7	3	10

Tangible Materials Sharing		
Required	Suggested	Total
8	5	13

Preregistration

As mentioned in the [Policies](#) section of this report, preregistration is often a requirement for clinical trials or other human subjects research. Some funders require preregistration only for clinical trials, and mention or recommend preregistration for other studies. This accounts for the three funders whose policies require preregistration for certain studies, and suggest preregistration for others. One funder without a codified or publicly available access-to-research policy, mentioned that preregistration is required as a process for their grantees.

Preregistration			
Required	Suggested	Required and Suggested	Total
3	3	3	9

ASAP clearly communicates its reasoning behind requiring preregistration for certain studies:

“We require that interventional research involving the collection of new data from human participants be registered at [clinicaltrials.gov](#) or a primary registry in the WHO registry network. This requirement is in line with item 35 of the WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Participants and the

International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) Recommendations. We also require registration of studies that include a primary aim to replicate a previous finding.¹⁴

It should be noted, however, that ASAP does not fund many of the studies that fall into this category. Rather, ASAP's policy is part of an effort to socialize the concept of preregistration with current ASAP researchers and other funders.

Noticeably only three funders outrightly require preregistration, one of which is an outlier in that while it has no codified access-to-research policy, awardees are required to preregister their studies. This particular funder supports psychological research, a discipline which has been heavily influenced by open science practices through the [Center for Open Science](#), which was founded and developed by research psychologists. One of the funders requiring preregistration, Arnold Ventures, provided the funding for the founding of the Center.¹⁵

Funder Identifiers, Award Identifiers, and Persistent Identifiers

While information systems and databases make use of unique identifiers, there is growing momentum to ensure that identifiers used are persistent. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are a kind of unique identifier that remain valid over time, even when objects may move digital locations.¹⁶ There are currently many efforts underway in the information landscape to improve the use of open metadata and metadata standards. For example, in the United States the National Information Standards Organization (NISO) US National PID Strategy Committee is working to develop a PID standard.¹⁷

There are several commonly used PIDs in the research ecosystem. ORCID iD is used for individual researchers or persons, ROR IDs are used for research organizations, and DOIs are used for digital objects such as articles, datasets, and other outputs. PIDs allow for linkages across multiple

¹⁴ Aligning Science Across Parkinson's, "ASAP Open Science Policy Handbook."

¹⁵ Center for Open Science, "Center for Open Science to Provide Revolutionary Approach to Scientific Communication," accessed February 20, 2026, <https://www.cos.io/about/news/center-open-science-provide-revolutionary-approach-scientific-communication>.

¹⁶ ORCID, "What Are Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)?," ORCID, accessed February 27, 2026, <https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/articles/360006971013-What-are-persistent-identifiers-PIDs>.

¹⁷ NISO, "NISO Proposal: US National PID Strategy," June 15, 2024, <https://groups.niso.org/higherlogic/ws/public/download/31525>.

products, contributors, and organizations, which allow for machine-readable linkages and the infrastructure to represent the rich nature of the linkages in the research ecosystem.

This policy analysis tracked whether identifiers were represented in funder policies, either as mentioned/suggested in the policy, or any kind of identifier use was required. It should be noted that the analysis tracked many identifiers, even those that are not persistent. For example, grants management systems include internal grant IDs, which often do not meet the technical requirements to make the identifiers persistent.

It is likely that the policy analysis results do not capture all uses of unique identifiers. Because the policy analysis examines policy documents for research outputs but not grant application requirements specifically, it is possible that the use of person identifiers such as ORCID iDs is under-represented in the analysis. For example, funders without existing access-to-research to policies may require applicants to supply ORCID iDs upon grant proposal submission, and did not supply that information for the analysis.

There are a variety of ways in which funder policies point to the use of PIDs and other metadata to assist with the discoverability and interoperability to research outputs and provenance. While some funders generally suggest the utility of metadata with phrases such as from the Gates Foundation policy, “...proper metadata tagging identifying Gates funding,” other funders specify specific repositories in which to deposit research that will assign persistent identifiers, most commonly DOIs. Other funder policies specify particular identifiers required or recommended to use.

Identifiers specified in funder policies			
<i>Person identifiers</i>	<i>Organization/Funder/Affiliation Identifiers</i>	<i>Award Identifiers</i>	<i>Output Identifiers</i>
ORCID iD	CRN (not persistent) ROR ID	DOI Accession Number (not persistent) Grant number (not persistent)	DOI RRID ARK

There is a robust movement to support open, interoperable metadata for research outputs, funding bodies, and awards. Metadata enables greater discoverability of research by users and can capture research provenance, including awards, to quickly find and display research outputs. For example, the Barcelona Declaration for Open Research Information includes funder and award metadata as part of its roadmap and is actively working to support funders in adopting and using PIDs to track funders and awards tied to research outputs. What’s more, OpenAlex is currently working on a Wellcome funded project that will make openly available funder and award metadata.¹⁸ Nonprofit open infrastructure providers such as DataCite, Crossref, and ORCID are actively working to improve and incorporate open metadata into the research corpus. Repositories such as openRxiv often allow funder information to be part of metadata records. As a result, funders can easily incorporate these efforts into their policies to recommend metadata best practices to awardees and examine their own internal systems for technological improvements to

¹⁸ Kyle Demes, “Funding Metadata in OpenAlex,” OpenAlex Blog, January 26, 2026, <https://blog.openalex.org/funding-metadata-in-openalex>.

support robust metadata that enables future discoverability of research by humans and machines alike.

Policy Development and Growth Since 2023

The 2026 funder policy analysis shows change and growth in funder policies from the 2023 analysis. When comparing suggestions to requirements for open practices in funder policies, we see growth in every area. Most notably, of funders with access-to-research policies, adoption of access to article requirements has increased by twenty-one percent and adoption of preprint requirements has increased by nineteen percent. Additionally, the percentage of funders requiring FAIR data practices increased from 29% in 2023 to 44% in 2026.

Likewise, the percentage of policies that suggested or recommended practices rather than requiring them significantly decreased. Although there was growth in preregistration requirements, suggested preregistration practices remain the same in both analyses. This is likely

due to the expanded scope of the data set, as well as the distinction between study types that require and those for which preregistration is suggested, but not required.

Given the political and technological disruptions affecting research, as well as U.S. Federal policy changes, we are likely to see changes in philanthropic access-to-research policies in the coming few years.

Recommendations for Funder Policies

There are five recommended actions pertaining to funder policies.

1. Eliminate embargo periods.
2. Partner with open infrastructure providers.
3. Explore data management plan requirements and support existing data principles and practices.
4. Strategically accelerate preprint adoption.
5. Develop incentives and workflows to complement policy requirements.

These recommendations reflect the direction in which policy practices for research funding are largely headed, taking into account actions supported by existing best practices, guidelines, governance, and community support.

1. Eliminate Embargo Periods

U.S. Federal funding agencies have developed and are currently implementing policies requiring the immediate sharing of research outputs and prohibiting embargo periods. Embargo periods impede the progress of discovery. In a rapidly changing scientific and knowledge production environment, embargos introduce additional barriers to accessing knowledge.

2. Partner with open infrastructure providers

There currently exist numerous initiatives and infrastructure providers that can support funders in implementing open practices. For example, most repositories for data, preprints, and other outputs assign persistent identifiers that can be made openly available and are machine-readable. Using open metadata such as ROR IDs, ORCID iDs, and DOIs would enable better monitoring of funder impacts and research outputs tied to awards as well as enable user discovery. Providers that assign and track PIDs are just one example in this category. Others may include search providers, publishing platforms, preprint servers, licensing standards, peer review communities, Open Educational Resource (OER) tools and more. One example of recent funder and infrastructure provider partnerships is the new partnership between Open Research Europe and CERN. Works funded by those in the Open Research Europe consortium will now be eligible to be hosted on CERN-maintained infrastructure.¹⁹

3. Expand data management plan requirements and support existing data principles and practices

Data sharing rapidly increases the progress of knowledge and research. Yet without thoughtful sharing that optimizes data discovery and usability, shared data cannot accelerate knowledge discovery. Instead, it may lead to wasted effort as researchers reproduce datasets for new analyses.

¹⁹ “CERN to Host Europe’s Flagship Open Access Publishing Platform,” CERN, March 26, 2026, <https://home.cern/news/news/cern/cern-host-europes-flagship-open-access-publishing-platform>.

Expanding data deposition policies to require the use of FAIR data practices would mitigate the sharing of data that cannot be used in future research due to integrity issues or other data quality problems. Moreover, supporting the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance will ensure that research data does not perpetuate further harms to indigenous people. Finally, data sharing requirements that translate into adopted practice are most successful when supported by robust training, education, and guidance to support awardees in meeting these expectations.

4. Strategically accelerate preprint adoption

The largest area of growth in funder policy open output adoption is the requirement or recommendation to share preprints. This is exemplified by the existing [Preprint Policy Framework](#) hosted by ASAPbio and created by the Creative Commons Open Science team in collaboration with funders and research-performing organizations. Preprints allow a decoupling of research sharing and research evaluation processes from the commercial publishing enterprise. Moreover, transparent peer review practices, data, and other research output sharing practices are currently being built for the preprint space. Given that the research and information-sharing landscape is rapidly changing in response to both political and technological disruptions, adopting preprint policies - either to replace or complement traditional open access policies - will ensure funders can readily participate in future innovations such as modular science and research sharing.

Experimental practices such as modular science and continuous science are rapidly maturing. Moreover, data and other research output sharing practices, along with transparent peer review practices, are becoming more deeply connected within preprint infrastructure. As such, funders with no experience with preprint deposits will be quickly left behind as other innovations are widely adopted.

5. Develop incentives to complement policy requirements

Policy requirements are one strategy to ensure open practice adoption. However, they should be instituted alongside complementary open practice incentives and workflows. Incentives are also a mechanism that can be used by funders, regardless of whether or not they have codified policies supporting open research.

While some researchers may be motivated by the altruism of open practice, others may be more extrinsically motivated. Introducing extrinsic motivations beyond policy compliance, such as public acknowledgment or commendations for open practices, may further incentivize adoption of open practices. As a complement, workflows that allow for ease of open practice implementation, such as processes for data deposit or compliance and reporting workflows, can signal the need for and support the adoption of open practices.

Next Steps

There are three concrete next steps ORFG is undertaking to better understand access-to-research policies and to support the funding community in developing, implementing, and socializing potential policy changes: monitor policy changes, socialize this report, and develop funder-focused playbooks for open research policy implementation and socialization.

First, ORFG will continue to monitor the rapidly evolving open output landscape and funder policies. The results presented in this report are from a discrete snapshot in time, and we can expect funder practices to evolve as technological innovations develop and as global social and political climates change.

Second, this document can and should be used to begin conversations within funding organizations, among researchers who rely on funding, higher educational institutions, and research performing organizations. As such, ORFG will work to share and socialize this report within the larger community interested in the ecosystem of open research outputs.

Finally, in the funder space, there is a clear need for guidance on developing, implementing, and socializing policy changes with internal and external stakeholders. As such, ORFG is developing funder-focused playbooks to support individuals working in the funder landscape, as well as funding organizations, in implementing and socializing open policies. Two playbooks are currently under development: a Preprint Policy Playbook and a Data Playbook. These playbooks will complement existing discussions and explorations in the current open ecosystem, such as the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering and Medicine [Roundtable on Aligning Incentives for](#)

[Open Scholarship](#) Action Collaborative 2: Toward a new research communication paradigm, and the [Preprint Policy Framework](#).

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Appendices

Appendix A: Methods and Scope

Funder policies for access to research were identified and analysed. Some of these policies are expressed in one document or policy, whereas others are expressed via several. For instance, funders may have separate intellectual property, data access, and output access policies. Policies were collected from publicly available websites, or shared by the funder directly with ORFG staff. A total of thirty-nine funders were analysed, twenty-five of which have codified open access or access-to-research policies discussing research outputs.

Using the previous funder landscape analysis as a starting point, the data collection scope was broadened to include non-ORFG member funders of open research outputs and practices. The data collection also tracked the use of identifiers such as those for people, outputs, funders, and awards; and information on organizational persistent identifier registry memberships as well as grant tracking and management systems.

Data was collected by reviewing published or funder policies shared internally with ORFG, then coded and represented in a Google spreadsheet. See the [data dictionary in Appendix B](#) for a list of data points. For contextual information regarding the data both the commenting feature and a notes field were used. This policy analysis did not specifically track policy mentions of monographs or monograph chapters as open outputs.

After an initial analysis was completed, funders were invited to review their organization's entry for accuracy and provided updates and corrections as needed.

Limitations

This analysis does have its limitations. While all included funders were invited to participate in the review of their organization's representation on the spreadsheet, not all funders offered feedback. Funders who are not presently ORFG members were also invited. Similarly, it is difficult to identify whether funders do require or recommend open research practices and outputs when

funders policy documentation is not made public, or when requirements are buried in several different policy documents. (For example, some funders may have an open policy and a separate data policy, etc.) As a result, the analysis is not comprehensive to include all philanthropic global research funders that support open outputs. As such, there could be out-of-date or erroneous data included in this analysis.

Because policy is highly contextual, not all findings can be accurately represented visually in charts and graphs. In some data categories multiple requirements can exist within individual policies. For example, some funders recommend or require different access practices depending on what kind of research is funded. This is often the case with clinical trial research, as US federal requirements for preregistration must be met. A funder may require preregistration, but only for a certain type of research. Similarly, different licenses may be recommended or required for various sorts of research outputs. Finally, some funders' open funding portfolios were closed during the data collection stage of this project, namely CZI and Navigation Fund. Their previous policies remain in the data set.

Appendix B: Data Dictionary

Data Point	Scope Note
Public Policy/ Notes	Link to publicly available policy
Has a policy?	Whether there exists a public policy.
File	Link to a copy of the policy in Emily's Google Drive
Funder Outputs Portal	Link to any publicly available output portal.
Date Last Updated	Date the policy was last updated
2025 Review	Whether the policy has been reviewed for updates to the analysis
Article Sharing Requirement	For formally published articles in journals.
Article Embargo	Any stated embargo period for published articles.
Article License	Any stated licenses required or mentioned in the policy.
Rights Retention	Whether or not language in a policy exists about authors' rights retention.
Preprints	Whether policies require or mention preprints.
Preprint License	Any stated license requirements for preprints.
Data Access	Any stated data deposit and access requirements.
Data Deposit Timing	Deposit timing requirements.
Data Access Scope	What data must be deposited or other notes on data access.
FAIR	Whether FAIR data principles are mentioned or required
Data License	Licensing requirements for data outputs
Data/ Resource Management Plan	Whether D/RMPs are in the policy and how.
KRT / Availability Statement	Whether Key Resource Tables or Availability statements are mentioned or required.

Data Point	Scope Note
Code Sharing	Code sharing requirements.
Code License	Code license requirements.
Preregistration	Preregistration requirements.
Protocol Sharing	Protocol sharing requirements
Protocol License	Licenses required for protocols.
Tangible Materials Sharing	Any tangible materials sharing requirements.
Output Identifiers	Any identifier requirements for outputs such as articles, data, and others.
Output Identifier Type	Any specific identifier mentioned or language regarding identifier standards.
Person Identifier	Whether a person identifier is mentioned or required
Person Identifier Type	What specific person identifiers are mentioned or required
Funder Identifier	Whether a funder identifier is required
Funder Identifier Type	What identifier is used for the funder
Award Identifier	Any award identifier mentions or requirements
Award Identifier Type	What award identifier is used.
PID Registry Membership(s)	Whether and to which organization a funder has a PID registry membership.
Grants Management Systems	What grants management and other systems used by the funder.
Output Systems	What, if any, system used to make outputs available.
Notes	Free text field for notes.

Appendix C: Funders with Publicly Available Policies

[Alex's Lemonade Stand Foundation](#)

[Templeton World Charity Foundation](#)

[Aligning Science Across Parkinson's](#)

[Volkswagen Foundation](#)

[American Heart Association](#)

[Wellcome](#)

[Arcadia Fund](#)

[Arnold Ventures](#)

[Astera Institute](#)

[Carlsberg Foundation](#)

[Chan Zuckerberg Initiative](#)

[Dam Foundation](#)

[Gates Foundation](#)

[Helmsley Trust](#)

[Hewlett Foundation](#)

[Howard Hughes Medical Institute](#)

[Michael J. Fox Foundation](#)

[Moore Foundation](#)

[Novo Nordisk](#)

[Open Society Foundations](#)

[Robert Wood Johnson Foundation](#)

[Simons Foundation](#)

Appendix D: Licenses

Licenses in funder policies			
Output Type	Number of policies	Number of Policies Suggesting or Requiring Licensing	Specific Licenses
Articles	23	16	CC-BY CC-BY 4.0 CC0 CC-BY-SA “Latest CC license” “Open Access license” CC-BY-ND (with agreed upon exception)
Data	21	15	CC license CC0 CC0 + BY CC-BY CC-BY 4.0 CC-BY-SA Conformant licenses “No more restrictive than CC-BY” “CC-BY or equivalent”
Code	16	8	“Open source license” “License that allows for reuse” “Open licensing” “MIT license or more open” MIT BSD 2-CLause BSD 3-clause Apache v.2.0 CC-BY or equivalent

Licenses in funder policies			
Output Type	Number of policies	Number of Policies Suggesting or Requiring Licensing	Specific Licenses
Preprints	14	9	CC-BY CC-BY-NC CC-BY 4.0 CC0 “CC-BY or more open”
Protocols	10	5	CC-BY “CC-BY or more open” CC0 “Open license”